

Contributorship and Authorship Roles

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[CRedit \(Contributor Roles Taxonomy\)](#) is a high-level taxonomy to ensure the recognition of authors and different kinds of contributions they make to the development of a research article or outcome.

I have adopted and extended the CRedit taxonomy for the Research Community Management team to guide the inclusion of a broad range of contribution types aiming to ensure fair recognition of their work as authors and contributors. All authors are contributors, but not all authors may be authors. However, all contributors should be given the opportunity to author the outputs shared as part of research.

The distinction between contributorship and authorship provided here should be used for setting a shared understanding as well as to communicate about opportunities available in the projects for all contributors.

1. Direct Contributor Roles for Authorship

Research stage	Definition	Direct Contributors	CM responsibilities
Design	Technical planning, expert recommendations, supervision or guidance, developing project roadmaps and milestones, tooling and template development	Project team (at the funding stage)	Set up a version controlled repository. Ensure all stakeholders have created ORCID and are aware of DOI (Digital Object Identifiers)
Conceptualisation	Ideas; formulation or evolution of overarching research goals and aims	PI, lead/core research team	Begin developing project charter with the vision defined at the conceptualisation stage
Methodology	Development or design of methodology; creation of models	lead/core research team as well as Community Manager (CM) and Research Software Engineers (RSE) if in team	Enable collaborative spaces such as coworking, team meetings, in-person scoping event, shared documentation and contribution guideline
Software	Programming, software development; designing computer programs; implementation of the computer code and supporting algorithms; testing of existing code components	lead/core research team, RSE	Ensure that open licensing has been recommended and included in the repository, provide a collaborative process for reference collection

Validation	Verification, whether as a part of the activity or separate, of the overall replication/ reproducibility of results/experiments and other research outputs - generalisable	lead/core research team, Research Engineers, CM, external reviewers (expert consultation such as from community)	Enable discussion on reproducibility, a support research team in collecting tools/methods to ensure reproducibility, involve Research Application Managers (RAM)
Investigation	Conducting a research and investigation process, specifically performing the experiments, or data/evidence collection	PI, lead/core research team	Create spaces for sharing progress, create a roadmap to share on the repository, provide community-wide reports or newsletters
Resources	Provision of study materials, reagents, materials, patients, laboratory samples, animals, instrumentation, computing resources, or other analysis tools	PI, lead/core research team, RSE, CM, RAM, IT, external partners	Coordinate with the project management team and contribute to a transparent record. Support partnership and sharing of resources. Ensure accessibility.
Data Curation	Management activities to annotate (produce metadata), scrub data and maintain research data (including software code, where it is necessary for interpreting the data itself) for initial use and later reuse (including licensing)	lead/core research team, partnering projects, data wranglers (if in place), RSE	Ensure GDPR/legal and ethical use of data, ensure open licensing or licensing agreement is in place. Provide access to TRE in collaboration with RSE. Ensure data protection guidelines are implemented and FAIR principles are applied. Share metadata on the repo.
Writing - Original Draft	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically writing the initial draft (including substantive translation)	lead/core research team, RSE, CM, RAM, and data stewards	Ensure a clear understanding of who will be authors. Ensure contributors are not left out. Apply an inclusive approach to authorship. Ensure open access avenues for the article. Establish agreement to submit preprint.

Writing - Review & Editing	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work by those from the research group, specifically critical review, commentary or revision – including pre-or post publication stages	All members (including invited reviewers) + comms team	Ensure that the choice of the co-authoring article is collaborative (shared online document). Give access to all contributors and reviewers. All contributors to research not involved in the writing stage should be invited at this stage. Keep a record of who the authors are and their contribution types.
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Visualisation	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically visualisation/ data presentation	lead/core research team, REG, and external contractors for hand sketched or digital graphics	Ensure code for data visualisation is shared with data. Support the use of literate programming with a description of data visualisation. Ensure centralisation and independent release of illustrations on Zenodo for reuse.
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Supervision	Oversight and leadership responsibility for the research activity planning and execution, including mentorship external to the core team	lead/core research team, REG	Ensure that the decision-making process and governance process are defined and communicated transparently.
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2. Contributorship - may also take author roles as described above

Term	Definition	Contributors	CM responsibilities
Project administration	Management and coordination responsibility for the research activity planning and execution	Programme Manager and Research Project Manager (PM Team)	Ensure alignment with community management tasks and goals. Ensure the findability of resources.
Funding acquisition	Acquisition of the financial support for the project leading to the research and publications	PI, lead/core research team, PM Team, CM	Ensure resourcing for community management and open science infrastructure. Embed open science/research considerations in the funding proposal.

Community Engagement Connecting with members, enabling collaboration, identifying resources etc	CM, PM Team, RAMs	This includes the core responsibilities of the community management	
Transparent Communication	Making all communication transparent for the stakeholders	CMs, PM Team, RAMs - supporting everyone	Establish and maintain processes and platforms for open communication (even when the project is not open)
Equity, Diversity, Inclusion (EDI) and Accessibility	Accessibility of resources, consideration of disability	PI, CMs, PM Team, EDI team/committee - supporting everyone	Embed considerations for EDI and accessibility in all community engagement and research process, platform, contents
Cross-exchange	Knowledge share, workshops, skill building events and resources	PI, CM, RAM - supporting everyone	Identify skill gaps and organise skill building and/or knowledge share opportunities. Offer basic technical training regularly, Hold coworking events to allow open discussion, code review, troubleshooting etc.
Ethics review	Ensure that if the research project needs to undergo an ethics review process	RPM, Ethics committee - supporting PI, researchers, CM, RAM	Contribute to the application process
Public engagement	Communications beyond the project and the Turing	CM, community members, communications team, RAMs	Attend and support the project's participation in external and international opportunities. Identify external stakeholders and help establish collaborations. Contribute to designing and delivering high-impact events for the dissemination of project outputs
Engagement with funders and policymakers	Pre-publication review, External advisory board meetings, regular reporting, post-publication reporting, reaching out to the relevant policy makers actively	PI and lead/core research team - supporting everyone	Contribute to communications and collaboration process

Recognition and credit	Assessing incentives, creating a fair value system, fair recognition of all contributors	PI, CM, Communication team	Ensure recognition and visible record keeping for acknowledging all contributors as guided by the reference articles and resources. Ensure a shared understanding for fair recognition and incentives.
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Reference

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 - Project Ownership; Making Research Objects Citable, Tips for Getting Authorship Right and Acknowledging Contributors; Research Infrastructure Roles; Creating project repositories.
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